

Kinetics of Oxidation of Caffeine by Bromamine-B in HCl Medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of caffeine by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide (bromamine-B; BAB) in HCl medium have been studied at 288 K. The rate shows a first order dependence on [BAB], fractional orders in [H⁺] and [Cl⁻] and is independent of [caffeine]. Addition of the reaction product, benzenesulphonamide and variation of ionic strength of the medium have no effect on rate. A decrease of the dielectric constant of the medium decreased the rate constant. The solvent isotope effect has been studied in D₂O medium. Activation parameters have been evaluated from the Arrhenius plots. Mechanisms proposed and the derived rate laws are in agreement with the observed kinetics.

Electrolytic oxidation¹ of caffeine in acidic solution has been reported. The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of caffeine by sodium *N*-chlorobenzenesulphonamide has been reported from our laboratory². But no information is available on the oxidation of caffeine by the corresponding bromine analogues. Hence, we report here the results of investigations on the oxidation of caffeine by sodium *N*-bromobenzenesulphonamide (bromamine-B; BAB, C₆H₅SO₂NBrNa.1.5H₂O) in HCl medium at 288 K.

Results and Discussion

With caffeine in large excess, plots of log [BAB] vs time were found to be linear indicating a first order dependence of rate on [BAB]. The pseudo-first order rate constants (*k*) are given in Table 1. The oxidation was carried out with different concentrations of caffeine at constant concentrations of [BAB] and [HCl]. The reaction rate was independent of initial concentration of caffeine indicating zero order with respect to caffeine.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF REACTANT CONCENTRATIONS ON THE RATE OF REACTION

[HCl] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 288 K

10 ⁴ [BAB] mol dm ⁻³	10 ² [caffeine] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ <i>k</i> s ⁻¹
8.0	1.0	1.22
9.0	1.0	1.22
10.0	1.0	1.20
11.0	1.0	1.18
12.0	1.0	1.19
10.0	0.5	1.21
10.0	1.0	1.20
10.0	2.0	1.24
10.0	3.0	1.22
10.0	4.0	1.21
10.0	5.0	1.18

At fixed [BAB] and [Substrate], the rate of reaction increased with increase in [HCl] (Table 2). Plot of log *k* vs

log [HCl] was linear with slope 1.38. Total [Cl⁻] in the reaction mixture was kept constant at 0.06 mol dm⁻³ by adding NaCl and then [H⁺] was varied using HCl. The rate increased with increase in [H⁺]. A plot of log *k* vs log [H⁺] was linear with a fractional slope 0.68. [H⁺] was maintained constant (0.01 mol dm⁻³) with HCl and rate increased with the addition of NaCl. A plot of log *k* vs log [Cl⁻] was linear with a fractional slope 0.70.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARYING [HCl], [H⁺] AND [Cl⁻] ON THE RATE OF REACTION

[BAB] = 10.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [caffeine] = 10.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, μ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³, temp. = 288 K

10 ² [HCl] mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ <i>k</i> s ⁻¹	10 ² [H ⁺]* mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ <i>k</i> s ⁻¹	10 ² [Cl ⁻]** mol dm ⁻³	10 ³ <i>k</i> s ⁻¹
0.5	0.45	1.0	1.52	1.0	1.20
1.0	1.20	2.0	2.40	2.0	1.95
2.0	2.90	3.0	3.00	4.0	3.09
3.0	4.65	4.0	4.04	6.0	4.14
4.0	6.36	5.0	4.92	8.0	5.20

* At constant [Cl⁻] = 0.06 mol dm⁻³. ** At constant [H⁺] = 0.01 mol dm⁻³.

Addition of NaBr (8 × 10⁻⁴–30 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³), the reaction product benzenesulphonamide (8 × 10⁻⁴–30 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³) and variation of ionic strength of medium by adding NaClO₄ (0.1–0.5 mol dm⁻³) had no effect on reaction rate. Solvent isotope effect was studied using D₂O as solvent medium. The rate of reaction *k*_{H₂O} is 1.20 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ and *k*_{D₂O} 1.68 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹. The rate increased in D₂O medium with a value of 1.40 for the inverse isotope effect. The solvent composition was varied by adding methanol (0–40%, v/v). The rate decreased with increase in the methanol content of the reaction mixture. A plot of log *k* vs 1/*D* gave a straight-line with a negative slope. The reaction rates were studied at different temperatures (283–298 K). Plots of log *k* vs 1/*T* were linear from which the energy of activation (*E*_a) and other kinetic and thermodynamic parameters were calculated (Table 3). Addition of reaction mixture to acrylamide did not initiate polymerization showing the absence of free radicals.

TABLE 3—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF CAFFEINE BY BAB IN HCl MEDIUM

Kinetic		Thermodynamic	
Reactant	Order	Parameter	Values
[BAB]	1.00	E_a	54.5 kJ mol ⁻¹
[Caffeine]	0.00	ΔH^\ddagger	52.2 kJ mol ⁻¹
[HCl]	1.38	ΔS^\ddagger	-114.0 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
[H ⁺]	0.68	ΔG^\ddagger	88.1 kJ mol ⁻¹
[Cl ⁻]	0.70	log A	9.7

Bromamine-B (RNBrNa, where R = C₆H₅SO₂⁻) is similar³ to CAT and behaves as a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions. The following equilibria will exist⁴ in acid solution for the oxidant.

The possible oxidising species in acidified BAB solutions are therefore RNHBr, RNBr₂ and HOBr. In the present system, if RNBr₂ were to be the reactive species, the rate law predicts a second order dependence⁵ of rate on [BAB], which is contrary to the experimental observations. Further, equation (5) indicates that the hydrolysis is slight and, if HOBr is primarily involved, a first order retardation of rate by the added benzenesulphonamide is expected. However, no such effect was noticed. Hardy and Johnston⁴ made detailed calculations on the concentration-dependence of conjugate acid, HOBr and BrO⁻ ion on pH, in aqueous BAB (6 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) in the pH range 7–13. It is seen from the results that [RNHBr] is high at pH 7 (4.1 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³), while [HOBr] ≈ 6.0 × 10⁻⁶ mol dm⁻³ and [BrO⁻] ≈ 10⁻⁷ mol dm⁻³. A comparison with the concentration of species present in acidified CAT solution³ would indicate that RNHBr is the likely oxidising species in acid medium for reacting with the substrate. Based on these facts, the oxidation of caffeine by BAB is presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Assuming total concentration of BAB as [BAB]_T = [RNHBr] + [X], one can get,

$$[\text{X}] = \frac{K[\text{BAB}]_T[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Since } \frac{-d[\text{BAB}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{X}] = \frac{Kk_1[\text{BAB}]_T[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}$$

$$k = \frac{Kk_1[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}{1 + K[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]}$$

where k is the observed rate constant,

$$\frac{1}{k} = \frac{1}{Kk_1[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]} + \frac{1}{k_1} \quad (8)$$

From the linear plot of 1/ k vs 1/[H⁺] at constant [Cl⁻] = 0.06 mol dm⁻³, the values of k_1 (9.09 × 10⁻³ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹) and K (317.0 dm³ mol⁻¹) were calculated.

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of caffeine by BAB is given in Scheme 2. The first step is the electrophillic attack by RNHBr at C-8 to form bromocaffeine, followed

Scheme 2

by solvolysis to X. Addition to the C₅-C₆ double bond solvolysis and hydrolysis gives alloxan and methyl urea. The negative dielectric constant effect probably supports dipole-dipole interaction⁶ in the rate-determining step. Since D₃O⁺ is about three times stronger than H₃O⁺ for acid catalysed reactions, the inverse isotope effect $k_{D_2O}/k_{H_2O} > 1$. The observed value 1.40 indicates⁷ the contribution of a primary isotope effect in the rate-determining step, where a O-D bond-breaking may be involved. The proposed mechanism is also supported by the moderate values of energy of activation and other thermodynamic parameters (Table 3). The fairly high positive values of free energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicate that the transition state is highly solvated, while the negative entropy of activation suggests the formation of the compact activated complex. The constancy of rate constant by the addition of neutral salt or reaction product (RNH₂) also supports the proposed mechanism.

The rates are found to be higher with bromamine-B than chloramine-B². This could be attributed to the difference in electrophilicities of the halogen cations Br⁺ and Cl⁺ involved in the oxidation process and is related to the ease with which these species can be formed in reactions.

Experimental

Bromamine-B was prepared by the reported procedure⁸. The purity of BAB was checked iodometrically through its active bromine content and the compound was further characterised by its ¹³C-FT-NMR spectrum using a Bruker WH spectrometer (270 MHz) with D₂O as solvent and TMS as the internal standard : 143.38 (C-1, carbon attached to S atom), 134.30 (C-4 *para* to the hetero atom), 131.26 (C-2,6) and 129.31 (C-3,5).

An aqueous solution of BAB was standardised iodometrically and preserved in brown bottles to prevent its photochemical deterioration. Caffeine (B.D.H.) was recrystallised before use and its aqueous solution prepared. All solutions were prepared by using double-distilled water and A.R. grade chemicals were used. Required ionic strength was maintained by adding NaClO₄ solution. Heavy water (D₂O; 99.2%) was supplied by the B.A.R.C., Bombay.

The reaction was carried out in glass stoppered pyrex boiling tubes whose outer surface was coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. Requisite amounts of caffeine,

hydrochloric acid, sodium perchlorate and water (to keep the total volume constant for all runs) were taken in the tube and thermostated at 288 K for thermal equilibrium. A measured amount of BAB solution was also thermostated at the same temperature and rapidly added to the mixture in the boiling tube. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric determination of unreacted BAB in a measured aliquot of the reaction mixture at different intervals of time. The course of the reaction was studied for about three half-lives. The rate constants calculated were reproducible to ±3%.

Stoichiometry : Reaction mixtures containing excess of [BAB] over [caffeine] were kept in the presence of 0.01 mol dm⁻³ HCl for 24 h. Estimation of unreacted BAB showed that one mole of caffeine consumed two moles of BAB,

where, R = C₆H₅SO₂⁻. One of the reaction products, benzenesulphonamide (RNH₂) was detected by tlc using petroleum ether-chloroform-1-butanol (2 : 2 : 1, v/v) as the solvent and iodine as the detecting agent (*R_f* = 0.88). Methylurea was identified⁹ by tlc using ethylacetate-chloroform-water (3 : 3 : 3) as the solvent and visualising with 5% iron(III) chloride in 1% potassium hexacyanoferrate(III). Alloxan was detected¹⁰ as a purple spot after spraying with ammonium iron(III) sulphate solution.

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